

D2.1

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presentation of the corpus studied

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In this report the ESR's try to situate their research so far within the framework of the present state of the arts which is close to their selected individual case studies. They all show how important the Islamic cultures of translation are, both in the field of religious texts, political ideologies, media and TV series and cultural traditions and in the transmission of knowledge about these fields.

Introduction

Two studies reflect on the role of language and bilingualism/multilingualism in contemporary Muslim societies with a special reference to the vernacular languages in Morocco and TV-series in Turkey.

The third case highlights how globalizing networks of Arabic and European scholars of Islam and its culture represent a unique example of cultural and academic encounters. In the colonial age, the translation and printing of books and periodicals were textual practices and processes central to the globalisation of Muslim societies.

Part 1.

Multilingualism, Language Contact and Politics: the Case of Morocco

By Eleonora Landucci (ESR 4)

In Islamic societies, Arabic is considered the koinè in the transmission of religious knowledge and messages. While the language of the Qur'an exerts its authority, multilingualism, which is present in several Muslim majority countries, still plays a central role in the production and transformation of religious discourses.

In this regard, Morocco represents an interesting case study that attracts the attention of numerous researchers in the field of linguistics, political science and social sciences (Kossmann 1997, 2002, 2020; Merolla 2008, 2019; Rouighi, 2019; Vicente, 2004, 2018; Ziamari, 2018; Soulaïmani, 2016; Caubet, 2003, 2016; Miller, 2013, 2016; Tilmantine, 2015; Maddy-Weitzmann, 2006, 2013; Lafkioui, 2008, 2013; Pouessel, 2012; Hoffmann 2002, 2006, 2010; Brugnatelli, 2005, 2008; Sadiqi, 2003; Basset, 1883). Morocco includes within its territory several vernacular varieties which are: Moroccan Arabic (Darija) - considered as the main language of communication nationwide - and the Moroccan Berber

varieties, spoken by between 24% and 47% of the population (Alalou, 2018). Moroccan Berber is divided, for practical purposes, into three main entities: Tashelhiyt, Tamazight and Tarifiyt (Kossmann, 2020). This linguistic, and cultural, pluralism shapes a country where Islam is the religion of the state; and the King, Mohammed VI, is constitutionally considered as Amîr Al-Mu'minyîn, "Commander of the faithful".

This particular situation has to be included in a political framework where the government's majority belongs to political Islam parties, as well as through the laissez-passer of the monarchy. Several authors explored the complex relation between Islamist political actors and the King's entourage (Bennani-Chraïbi, 2017; Macías-Amoretti, 2017, 2015; Mahdi, 2013; Maddy-Weitzman & Zisenwine, 2013; Silverstein, 2012; Ferrié 2012; Belal, 2011; Darif, 2010; Burgat, 1995; Leveau, 1985; Waterbury, 1975). The political scientist Mohamed Tozy (1999) explored this relation by underlying how the Moroccan political system is shaken by a double tension which, in his views, neutralises any inclination

for radical transformation. On the one hand, we observe the rooting of an authoritarian culture which applies to the monarchy as well as to the political class; on the other hand, the centrality of religion is sustained as legitimising mechanism of the power in place. These parties are represented as a milestone of social counter-projects which can be found in the political Islam movements and parties of the late 1980s.

Following the same perspective, historians such as Pierre Vermeren (2012) have pointed out that after the independence from the French Protectorate (1956) the political discourse revolved around the process of Islamisation as Arabisation as the core element of the national identity construction. However, it is during the reign of King Hassan II when this process was systematised through the linguistic policies behind the reforms of the national education system (Gérard and Schlemmer, 2003). A significant turning point came with the coronation of King Mohammed VI, who, wishing to assume the image of a reforming and progressive

leader as opposed to that of his father, favoured a climate of relative freedom of expression. This signified a certain openness towards cultural and religious minorities, as evidenced by the recognition (Constitution 2001 - article 5) of Berber as one of Morocco's official languages. In his view, historian Bruce Maddy-Weitzman (2006) states that language and vernacularity in this period became significant political instruments for the identity re-appropriation and, in some cases, for contesting the existing regime.

Others scholars, such as Thierry Desrués (2018), have noticed how language and language policies became an instrument for the government to reconnect with the territories where the linguistic majority is represented by the Berber varieties, such as the Rif region (Northern Morocco) historically in contrast with the Makhzen. In this regard, the IRCAM (the Royal Institute of Amazigh Culture) was committed with the task to standardise Berber languages and promote Berber culture. This institute has been seen as a final attempt by the state to reclaim Amazigh

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militancy, and as a way to dodge its politicisation (Tozy, Lakhsassi, Ait Mous et al., 2006). Thus, linguistic plurality in Morocco reveals to be a crucial issue from a social, cultural and political points of view, since it brings out many frictions and adjustments undergoing within the institutional power and the different sectors of the society.

In this sense, anthropologists and sociolinguists, such as Dominique Caubet and Catherine Miller, were interested in the use of different vernaculars as an instrument of political subjectivation (Foucault, 2008). In their works on youth languages and slangs in the suburban areas of Moroccan cities, they analysed the ways in which different languages – Berber varieties, Spanish, French, English – were manipulated and integrated in the everyday verbal forms of communication within youth generations (Caubet and Miller, 2013; 2016). Processes of language transformation and mediation have been studied also by sociolinguists, such as Daniela Merolla and Mena Lafkioui, especially with their focus on digital spaces on Internet. Their

analysis on the reconstruction of Amazigh orality on websites (Lafkioui and Merolla, 2008) showed how Internet mediated exchanges facilitated the spread of “Amazigh cultural and metacultural productions.” However, at the same time, this encourages the reproduction of a “cultural “heritage” crystallised in “hegemonic ideological discourses of cultural exclusivity” (Merolla and Lafkioui, 2008, p. 12).

Finally, language has been also examined through the prism of gender. In the analysis of Fatima Sadiqi (2003) and Katherine Hoffman (2002) the understanding of gender perception and women’s agency can be achieved only by taking into account the structure of power in a specific culture, and language is an important component of this power. According to these scholars, factors such as social differences, contextual differences, and identity differences interact in the daily linguistic performances of gender.

To conclude, the authors mentioned in this report greatly contributed to analysing the pivotal role of language in the cultural, social and political processes at stake in Moroccan society. However, further research has to be conducted on the ways in which Islam - understood both as religious belief, as a code of moral conduct, and as the ideological basis for a political thought - is conveyed through the linguistic varieties, and the vernacularity present in contemporary Morocco.

Part 2.

(Un)tangling the Muslim Presence in Europe: a history of cultural translation

By Elmozfar Abdelhafiz (ESR 5)

In today's Europe, a very particular divergence between public and scholarly historiographies seems to be steadily growing. Nowhere is this more evident than in the heavily debated and contested field/concept of globalization. Following its explosive growth of popularity in the social sciences and humanities during the late 1990s and early 2000s, the term has seeped into everyday use as an indispensable component of the political and public discourses of almost every country around the world.

My research is a study into a particular instance of globalization. It centers on Islam as an objectified image in constant negotiation and contestation by different global actors. As such, I do not view Islam as a static essential image. On the contrary, I am far more interested in the historical process by which the image(s) of Islam was accepted by different global actors - for very different reasons and logics - as holistic, timeless, and essential.

Operationally speaking, my research investigates into the formation and consequences of a very specific type of a global network of transculturality. By examining the very globalized and globalizing networks of Arabic and European scholars of Islam and its culture, we peek into a very formative period of the transcultural perception between Europe and the Mashriq (Abu-Lughod: 2011).

Posed against a background of increasing migration of Muslim individuals and families to Europe as workers and refugees in the post WWII era, the fuzzy and diverse meaning of the term "globalization" came to mean something rather specific in the public European mind. Instead of being a multidirectional historical process that has been increasingly present in human history, it is often restricted in the public discourse to mean the unidirectional movement of dark-skinned Muslim bodies from the Orient/Global-South along with their exotic/regressive culture towards Europe. This image of a besieged and penetrated Europe whose culture and values are under the threat of eradication

was embraced by the increasingly conservative and right leaning politics of post-Cold-War Europe (Zolberg: 1993). Yet, rigorous and scientific historical studies on globalization in general, and Europe's relationship with Islam in particular, show a radically different picture.

Starting with how globalization is to be defined at large, we owe a big debt to a plethora of anthropological studies of almost endless diversity that has brought attention to globalization as a lived experience present in the cultural and social life of individuals and small social units (See: Appadurai: 2010; Friedman: 1994). These ethnographic studies have enabled us to think of the large totality that is globalization as a very complex and diverse set of pixels and connections that are not necessarily coherent at first glance. And it is precisely here that a more specified inquiry into globalization as composed of multiple historical processes is useful and revealing.

The emergence of a framework of "entangled history" -along with its related perspectives of Histoire croisée and transnational history - reflected the observations and attitude of the aforementioned anthropological approach to globalization (Werner & Zimmermann 1993). In rethinking topics, such as the hyper-global trades of sugar (Mintz: 1985; 2007), coffee (Sözen: 2020), and even human slaves (Linebaugh & Rediker: 2013), and the significance of two particular analytical categories became more apparent than ever. The first - and most fundamental in my opinion- is mobility. The entangled history of the global interaction is argued to be best understood in terms of the mobility and dynamicity of the goods, ideas, and human bodies involved in it. The second significant analytical category in this framework of entanglement is directionality. With the shift of focus towards the mobility of human phenomena and the channels thereof, the tangle of movements in any channel would never be satisfactorily explained with a uni- or even bidirectional analysis. A highly globalized episode, such as

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the Atlantic slave trade, can no longer be simply explained in the bidirectional terms of European ships carrying weapons in one direction and slaves on the other. The same applies to the Muslim Hajj, while we examine how it took place in a colonial context connecting East to West, Europeans to Muslims and even non-European non-Muslims, it is no longer adequate to approach the Muslim pilgrimage as a simple bidirectional mobility of Muslim bodies to Mecca and back home. The multi-directionality of an entangled history approach enables a more comprehensive and multilayered compilation of historiographies that are more collaborative on a methodological level.

In the particular case of the history of Islam and Muslims in Europe and their relationship to it, a fresh and vibrant academic debate has been steadily growing in the recent years. As diverse as they might seem at first glance, when read together, the works of Ryad (2014, 2016), Kane (2015), Sajid (2015), Slight (2015), Jung (2011) illustrate the vast explanatory potential enabled by the modular and collaborative characteristics of an entangled history approach.

Part 3.

Exporting Cultural Products: Turkish TV Series in Global Context

By Mustafa Oguzhan Colak (ESR 6)

The emergence of communicative technology is a response to shifting social, political, and economic demands of modern society. It creates a new way of cultural interaction and shapes social and cultural life. TV series are one of the most important examples of this kind of cultural exchange. Scholars from departments of Media Studies, Cultural Studies, Sociology, and Communication mostly examined TV serials from different perspectives. The first examples of works focused on popular culture, ideology, propaganda, representation of women, the re-creation of history and nation, audio-visual narrative, political economy, and post-truth.

Today, Turkish TV series is highly prevalent worldwide, and the second most exported cultural products in the international TV series sector. Although from the 1990s onward, Turkish TV series have been primarily exported to the Middle East and Balkans, researchers' discovery of this new trend is pretty recent in the 2010s. There is a vast literature on the topic, and the popularity of the

series keeps attracting people from different fields. This report summarizes academic works and their main arguments on the Turkish TV series, which have high social and cultural impact on the Islamic world.

Turkish TV series have a high economic and political impact on the Islamic world, Latin America, and the Balkans. Turkey has become a new peripheral center of production in the industry after the United States, Latin America, and South Korea. The popularity of the Turkish TV series also attracts people, who consequently become more willing to visit historical places and the "lovely" nature represented on the TV. (Baran, 2018). The expansion of Turkish TV series worldwide stems from their high production quality, unique contents, agency agreement with copyrights, suitable formats for families. Especially, Arab women are impressed by the presentation of strong and independent Turkish women in the series. Turkish culture is also not much different from other Muslim communities, making people more interested in Turkish drama series. (Beğendik, 2020)

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The politicization of drama series is also one of the most discussed topics in Turkish TV series. Producers have employed their television dramas in building national identity by mobilizing national sentiments all over the world. Turkish TV series also appear as a sphere of political contest and mostly emphasized neo-Ottomanism and Islamic piety (Emre Çetin, 2014). As popular culture products, TV series effectively reproduces the state and nationalist ideologies through latent and manifest messages (Erçifci, 2018). Many scholars agree that the government is imposing its neo-Ottomanist ideology on the public by means of popular historical drama series (Çevik, 2019; Özçetin, 2019; Ergin & İleri, 2020). On the other side, some drama series criticize the government's policies against strict censorship. They employ some creative tactics to create a unique jargon by aiming to reach an intelligent and active audience (Lüküslü, 2018).

Conspiracy theories are also one of the main features of Turkish series. It is common to see in many Turkish TV

serials that some ancient secret organizations desire to control the state. So, this is why producers want to impose their socio-political content on the public through TV series. High political parallelism in the series also paves the path to demolish the thin line between reality and fiction (Bruijn, 2018). Another meaningful way for impressing the audience is to activate the series politically. For instance, popular actors of historical drama series broadcasted by Turkish state channel publicly proclaimed their support for President Erdogan before the presidential election. (Carney, 2018)

There are many Turkish written articles and dissertations on Turkish TV series in the fields of linguistics, political science, and social sciences. Unfortunately, even people in the field mostly speak Turkish can access and understand Turkish literature. These studies are barely open for international academia due to the language barrier. Turkish academics primarily focus on the popular culture and TV series' social, cultural, political, and economic effects on the audience (Kırtepe, 2014;

Karaboğa, 2016; Olgundeniz & Bilis: 2019; Tarhan & Karakoç, 2020). Many other researchers conducted researches on content analysis and technical evaluation on the TV drama series (Övür, 2013; Nisan & Bekiroğlu, 2016; Çetindağ, 2018; Çağıl & Kara 2019). Moreover, there are also some other researches on different topics such as the representation of the woman and gender roles in the drama series (Akkaya, 2016), audience analysis (Karaduman & Aciyan, 2019), global impacts of Turkish TV series (Akova: 2014), spiritualism, and Sufi stories (Çiftçi, 2019) in the series.

Finally, the Turkish TV series is highly effective in Islamic societies in terms of social, cultural, political, and ideological perspective, and a hot topic in the field. Many scholars examine the series from different perspectives, such as post-truth, political economy, politicization, and ideology. Even though the literature on the topic is enormous, they still represent a challenge for scholars. For instance, the audience lives worldwide, which creates an obstacle for scholars to do an

audience analysis. In my opinion, employing new computational methods and scraping data on social media platforms provides crucial solutions to deal with reaching a geographically dispersed audience for researchers.

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